

inside the cage as food for the moths. Moths were allowed to oviposit for 3-4 d. Fifteen days after release of the moths, the leafroller damage was assessed by counting the number of damaged leaves with reference to total leaves in each row, and infestation percentage was calculated. Based on

infestation percentage, the accessions were rated for damage using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

The same accessions were screened in the field in two replications, at Pondicherry where leafroller infestation was high.

Accessions RP2068-18-4-5, IR4707-

106-3-2, ARC6650, ARC10660, TNAU LFR832035, and TNAU LFR831331 had a damage rating of 3 both in seedling screening and in the field. RP2068-18-2-9, TNAU LFR832036, and TNAU LFR 831311 had a score of 3 in seedling screening and 1 in the field (see table). *S*

Promising long-duration lowland rices with resistance to key insect pests of kharif rice

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Host plant resistance to insect pests and diseases is the key to increased productivity of lowland kharif rice. Several promising lines from the crosses CR260 (CR151-79/CR1014), CR254 (Haldia-Magura/CR151-79), CR256

(Haldia-Magura/Pankaj) and CRM10 (Mahsuri mutant) adapted to lowlands (water stagnation of up to 60 cm), of long duration (145-180 d), and with good grain quality and high yields (3-5 t/ha) were identified in recent years at CRRI. In wet season, however, the yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker and the gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason limit production in many rice tracts. Pest-resistant cultivars can stabilize rice yields in these regions. We identified such cultivars from a set of 72 promising lines

from the above crosses.

In six cultivars of CR260 grown in lowlands at CRRI in 1981 and 1982 kharif together with yield standards in replicated trials, stem borer incidence at heading was very high, up to 28.5% whiteheads (WH) in 1981 and 27.6% in 1982. Cultivar CR260-30 was outstanding and superior to the others with zero WH in 1981 and 0.3% in 1982.

In 1983 kharif, all 72 lines were field tested. Plants were infested by implanting 4 healthy, laboratory-laid 4-d-old borer egg masses per plant on 4 growing plants per cultivar 50-75 d after planting (DAP) (2 at 50-55 DAP, 1 at 65 DAP, and 1 at 75 DAP). Percentage of deadhearts (DH) was as high as 78.8; WH, 75.8; and gross borer infestation, 77.3. The following cultivars were identified as outstandingly superior to the others and superior to or on par with the resistant checks: CR260-163-238, CR260-151-81-2-710, CR260-176-1-702, CR260-167-247-179, CR260-228, and CR260-30 (Table 1). Sashyashree released as resistant to stem borer was highly susceptible with the egg mass implantation technique.

We tested all 72 cultivars in another replicated field trial in 1983 kharif. Plants were transplanted in Jul at 15 × 15 cm spacing, with high fertilizer input (150 + 50 + 50 kg N/ha). Lights were installed and 3-5 cm standing water was maintained to induce high gall midge infestation (up to 100% infested hills and 39.3% silvershoots) in susceptible Jaya. Although no entry was highly resistant, CR260-21-2-716, CR260-21-715, CR254-43-126, CR256-31-36, CR254-43-42-3, and CR260-30 were the least susceptible and significantly superior to the other cultivars and the susceptible check (Table 2).

Table 1. Some promising stem borer-resistant late-duration cultivars with implantation of egg masses on growing plants in field, kharif 1983, CRRI.^a

Cultivar	DH (%)	WH (%)	Infestation (%)	Height (cm)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Grain type
CR260-163-238	21.3	2.6	15.0	120	150	4.5	LS
CR260-151-81-2-710	14.3	nil	9.7	115	145	3.5	MS
CR260-176-1-702	22.4	3.1	17.3	125	150	4.0	MS
CR260-167-247-179	23.0	nil	10.0	125	155	4.0	MS
CR256-30-211-2-708	58.7	14.3	47.9	120	155	3.5	MS
CR260-151-224	80.0	nil	76.4	120	155	4.5	LS
CR260-228	29.6	NA	29.6	120	150	4.0	LS
CR260-30	22.5	5.0	17.4	130	185	4.5	MS
IR9828-23-1 (R check)	27.0	22.2	25.0				
IR15723-45-3-2-2-2 (R check)	28.6	27.8	28.0				
Jaya (S check)	51.7	73.1	61.8				
Sashyashree	78.8	75.8	77.3				

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible, DH = deadhearts, WH = whiteheads, NA = not available, LS = long slender, MS = medium slender.

Table 2. Some promising gall midge-tolerant late-dulation cultivars. CRRI, 1983 kharif.

Cultivar	Mean % silvershoots	Angular values	Height (cm)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Grain type ^a
CR260-21-2-716	14.6	22.43	110	145	4.0	MS
CR260-21-7 15	15.1	22.72	110	145	4.0	MS
CR254-43-126	12.4	21.50	130	155	4.5	SB
CR256-31-36	12.7	20.55	100	140	4.0	SB
CR254-43-42-3	12.5	22.73	130	155	4.0	SB
CR260-30	11.3	19.36	130	185	4.5	MS
CR260-85-230	31.7	34.23	120	160	4.0	MS
Jaya (susceptible check)	39.3		90	135	3.0	LB
CD 0.05		7.25				
CD 0.01		9.62				

^aMS = medium slender, SB = short bold, LB = long bold.

CR260-30 was promising against both gall midge and yellow stem borers. Because of excellent grain quality, stable high yields, pest resistance, and tolerance for periodic submergence during flash floods, CR260-30 and other resistant cultures have become widely accepted by the lowland rice farmers of Orissa in recent years. *J*

Field evaluation of rices for resistance to thrips

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Rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall) cause serious damage to rice at the seedling stage and to the transplanted crop. Thrips incidence is severe during Jul-Sep at Coimbatore. We evaluated 62 rice accessions received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) for field resistance to thrips during Sep 1985. Each accession was planted in a 3-m-long row at 20 × 15 cm spacing. The susceptible check TN1 was planted after every 10 accessions. The accessions were not replicated. Thirty days after planting, the accessions were rated for damage using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Of the 62 rice accessions screened, 14 had resistance (score of 1) to *Baliothrips biformis*: IET7568, IE-1-7575, IET8659, IET8661, IET9177, Manoharsali, RP2068-18-26, RP2068-18-2-9, RP2068-18-4-2, RP2068-32-2-3, RP2069-3-5-2-2, VRS286-4-1, WGL47969, and WGL47970.

Screening of rice cultivars against rice whorl maggot (RWM)

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In 1984 kharif, 219 rice cultivars were screened against RWM *Hydrellia*

philippina Ferino in the National Screening Nursery Programme at Masodha. At 20 d after transplanting, damage reached a maximum of 51% in KP20. Among the entries. 7 had more

than 40% damage and were considered highly susceptible; 42 scored between 15 and 25% damage and were considered moderately resistant. None had below 15% damage (see table). *J*

Cultivars rated as highly susceptible and moderately resistant to RWM. Faizabad, India, 1984 kharif.

Designation	Cross combination	Leaf damage (%)
<i>Highly susceptible</i>		
RP20	Jaya/ARC5848	51.0
RP21	Jaya/ARC5848	46.5
NDR88-1-1	IR36/T21	42.8
HKRII3	—	42.7
HAUK6-11-1-1-1	IR28/Basmati 370	42.7
TNAU83735	TKM6 mutant	42.3
RP1579-1613-35	RPW6-17/ARC6650	41.3
<i>Moderately resistant</i>		
CR13-3512-8	—	15.7
IR1820-154-3-2-2-3	—	16.7
RNR10208	—	16.7
CR404-20	—	17.1
RP1641-594-2 B	Vikram/Benong III	17.5
RP2199-271-13	TKM6/Phalguna	18.2
RP2091-272-4-5-3	IR32/Phalguna	18.4
MTU534122	—	18.5
NRL 88-95	—	18.9
NDR309	IR36/Saket-1	19.3
OR489-80-22	IR2070-1054/Shakti	19.6
SYE104-9-32	SKL6/Kakeri	21.5
OR448-7-1	ORI58-7-1/IR28	21.4
TNAU83095	TNAU6464/TKM9	21.4
VL27	—	21.7
HKR117	—	21.7
PR25	Jaya/BR34	21.8
BAU149-2	Bala/Blackgora	21.9
KJT2-32-43-20	KJT-2-3243-20/K 35-3//RPW-6-15	21.9
RP1125-629-2-1	RPW 6-13/Ptb 2	22.0
BAU149-27	Bala/Blackgora	22.5
BAU152-64-7	IR2058-436/IR854-65// IR2070-423-2-56	22.6
DSI 15	—	22.6
BAU11-54	Mutant 14/IET5374	22.9
CR406-16	—	22.9
OR371-IP-2	Obs 677/IR2070-423-5	23.1
BS54	Bhawani/IR20	23.2
SYE158-32-36-23	Tuljapur-I/Cauvery	23.2
CRM10-4733-11-422	—	23.2
OR451-3-2	Dasal/OR132-127	23.5
RP2087-14-6-12.4	IET5854/IET6314	23.5
RNR89128	—	23.5
UPR82-83	—	23.5
BAU147-2-2	Mutant gora/N22	23.5
VRS163-2-2-3	—	23.8
IR28224-66-3-2	—	24.2
RNR64118	—	24.2
BAU149-2A	Bala/Blackgora	24.2
OR377-85-6	IR2061628-2-6-4-3/N22	24.4
TNAU83736	TKM6 mutant	24.5
PR27	—	24.6
TNAU83091	TNAU6464/TKM9	24.7

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